

R code of the simulation study for "A statistical approach in personalized nutrition exemplified by reanalysis of public datasets"

Paola G. Ferrario, Maik Döring, and Christian Ritz

January 10, 2025

This document contains all R lines (and resulting output) for the conduction of a simulation study. The aim of these simulations is to calculate the bias of the estimator presented and discussed in the above mentioned article.

```
library(lme4)
simulate.data<-function(beta0=c(0,0,0,0),
                        beta1=c(1,1,1,1),
                        sample.size.A=50,
                        sample.size.B=50,
                        num.iterations=1000,
                        seed="F"){
  n<-sample.size.A+sample.size.B
  data.sim<-data.frame(ID=factor(paste("ID",rep(1:n,each=2))),
                      time=factor(rep(c("t1","t2"),n)),
                      trt=factor(c(rep("A",sample.size.A),(rep("B",sample.size.B)))),
                      timXtrt=NA,x1=NA,y=NA)
  data.sim$timXtrt<-interaction(data.sim$time,data.sim$trt)
  names(beta0)<-unique(data.sim$timXtrt)
  names(beta1)<-unique(data.sim$timXtrt)
  if(is.numeric(seed)){set.seed(seed)}
  estimated.coef<-matrix(NA,nrow=num.iterations,ncol=8)
  for (i in 1:num.iterations){
    data.sim$x1<-rep(runif(n,0,40),each=2)
    random.intercept<-rnorm(n,0,sd=1)
    data.sim$y<-beta0[data.sim$timXtrt]+
      beta1[data.sim$timXtrt]*data.sim$x1+
```

```

    random.intercept[data.sim$ID]+
    rnorm(2*n,mean=0,sd=1)
  pn.lmm <- lmer(y ~ timXtrt-1 + timXtrt:x1 - x1 +(1|ID), data = data.sim)
  estimated.coef[i,]<-coef(summary(pn.lmm))[ ,1]
}
true.coef<-c(beta0, beta1)
names(true.coef)<-paste("b",rep(c("0","1"),each=4),".",names(true.coef),sep="")
average.bias<-apply(estimated.coef,2,mean)-true.coef
sd.bias<-apply(estimated.coef,2,sd)
average.bias.perc<-100*average.bias/true.coef
sd.bias.perc<-100*sd.bias/true.coef
coef<-rbind(true.coef,
            average.bias,
            average.bias.perc,
            sd.bias,
            sd.bias.perc)
meta<-c("sample.size.A"=sample.size.A,
        "sample.size.B"=sample.size.B,
        "num.iterations"=num.iterations,
        "seed"=seed)
return(list("coef"=coef,"meta"=meta))
}
#####
#####
#####
# Example 1
out<-simulate.data(beta0=c(10,12,13,11),
                  beta1=c(0.3,0.8,0.2,0.6),
                  sample.size.A=50,
                  sample.size.B=50,
                  num.iterations=1000,
                  seed=10052023)
write.csv2(out[["coef"]],file="simu_sampleSize_example1-v2.csv",quote=FALSE)
#####
#####
#####

```

```

# Example 2
beta0.sets<-list(c(10 ,12 ,13 ,11),
                c( 9 ,12 ,14 ,10),
                c( 9.5,11.5,12.5,10.5))
beta1.sets <- list(c(0.3,0.6,0.2,0.6),
                  c(0.4,0.5,0.3,0.7),
                  c(0.5,0.6,0.3,0.8))
n.h<-c(60,120,180,10000)

size.b<-length(beta0.sets)
size.n<-length(n.h)
n.h<-rep(n.h,times=size.b)
beta0.sets<-rep(beta0.sets,each=size.n)
beta1.sets<-rep(beta1.sets,each=size.n)
bias.list<-mapply(simulate.data,
                  beta0=beta0.sets,
                  beta1=beta1.sets,
                  sample.size.A=n.h,
                  sample.size.B=n.h,
                  num.iterations=1000,
                  seed="F",
                  SIMPLIFY=FALSE)

out<-data.frame(
  t(as.data.frame(lapply(bias.list,function(x) x[["meta"]]))),
  t(as.data.frame(lapply(bias.list,function(x)
    c(x[["coef"]][["true.coef"],],
      x[["coef"]][["average.bias.perc"],],
      x[["coef"]][["sd.bias.perc"],])
  )))
)
rownames(out)<-NULL
colnames(out)[ 5:12]<-paste(colnames(bias.list[[1]]$coef),".true.coef")
colnames(out)[13:20]<-paste(colnames(bias.list[[1]]$coef),".bias.mean.perc")
colnames(out)[21:28]<-paste(colnames(bias.list[[1]]$coef),".bias.sd.perc")
out<-out[,c(1:4,unlist(lapply(5:12,function(x) seq(x,28,8))))]
write.csv2(out,file="simu_sampleSize_example3-v2.csv",quote=FALSE)

```